

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE REGULATION OF LEGAL AID IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The provision of legal aid is crucial to ensure access to justice. It is therefore crucial that institutions responsible for providing legal aid services are effective. In Nigeria, the institutional framework for the provision of legal aid in Nigeria include governmental agencies like the Legal Aid Council as well as private organisations. Consequently, it becomes essential to analyse the role of these institutions in ensuring access to justice and their effectiveness. This thus forms the basis of this article titled. 'Effectiveness of the Institutional Framework for the Regulation of Legal aid in Nigeria.' This article adopts the doctrinal methodology with the use of primary and secondary sources as found in books, journal articles, newspapers and online sources. It discusses the initiatives, activities and outreaches carried out by the Legal Aid Council and explores various challenges that impede the effectiveness of the operations of the Legal Aid Council in Nigeria. The article discovers that challenges like inadequate funding, geographical inaccessibility and systemic inefficiencies impede the effectiveness of institutions providing legal aid. The article concludes that institutions providing legal aid are functional and effective however there is great room for improvement by addressing the challenges faced by the council. The article therefore provides some recommendations to improve the effectiveness of the Legal Aid Council in Nigeria.

Keywords: Access to Justice; Effectiveness; Equality; Institutions; Legal Aid; Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Sometime back, there was a need to visit the Ijebu-Ode correctional centre.¹ One thing that was conspicuous in the correctional centre's premises was a big charcoal board on which the number of inmates, convicted and detained was written with chalk. The majority of people in that prison were not convicted but had been remanded in the prison for more than a year. This was because they could not afford the services of legal practitioners. The question that should be asked is why does this problem exist despite the fact that there are institutions that provide legal aid? These institutions are both government and private institutions and one of their aims is to provide legal aid to those in need. Legal aid is simply providing legal services at no cost or at a discounted cost to those in need.

Section 36 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 grants individuals charged with criminal offenses the entitlement to defend themselves either personally or with the assistance of legal practitioners of their choice.² This provision guarantees the right to legal representation, allowing individuals to be represented by a lawyer in court. Although individuals have the option to represent themselves in court, practical realities often reveal the

necessity of having a legal representative. Thus, legal representation is crucial.

In the case of *Udo v The State*³, the court emphasised the essence of the right of fair hearing. It stated that due to the nature of a capital offence, individuals charged with such should be entitled to legal representation. The essence of this is to ensure that an accused is not unnecessarily exposed to a legal disadvantage. Although the court specifically addressed capital offence, one wonders whether this statement applies to other criminal matters and even civil cases.

Numerous individuals in Nigeria are unable to afford legal representation due to poverty and a lack of awareness regarding alternative avenues available to them. In order to address this issue, the government has established institutions that provide legal aid services. Additionally, non-governmental institutions also provide legal aid services. Therefore, it is apparent that in Nigeria, the framework for legal aid encompasses a range of institutions, both governmental and non-governmental, that work collectively to provide legal assistance to those in need. The effectiveness or otherwise of the institutional framework is what this article seeks to address.

Conceptual Analysis

Legal Aid is the provision of legal services, assistance, and resources to individuals, by both governmental and non-governmental entities with the aim of defending and empowering individuals on their legal rights and ultimately promoting a fair and inclusive legal system. This definition is posited because it extends the concept of Legal Aid as going beyond financial limitations especially where it is difficult to determine the threshold or what exactly qualifies as financial limitations and recognizing that all individuals should have the opportunity to seek legal advice and representation when faced with legal challenges or disputes.

Additionally, it also recognizes that institutional framework for legal aid comprises governmental institutions as well as other private organizations, including non-profit entities, community-based initiatives, pro bono networks, and legal clinics. Essentially, the definition reveals that the scope of legal aid encompasses a wide range of legal matters and embodies the principle of access to justice as a fundamental right. This one could say is the spirit and true meaning of the concept of 'legal aid'.

Legal aid plays a pivotal role in ensuring access to justice as it serves as a crucial mechanism to ensure that justice is not a privilege reserved for those with financial means. Within the context of access to justice, the fundamental principle is to provide equal and meaningful access to legal processes and remedies for all members of society, irrespective of their socioeconomic status. Legal aid, therefore, becomes a cornerstone in realizing this principle by addressing the inherent disparities in financial resources that often create barriers to accessing the legal system.

The Legal Aid Council of Nigeria, being the principal body tasked with providing legal aid, is intended to play a pivotal role in advancing access to justice within the country and its primary objective is to offer legal aid services to individuals who cannot afford private legal representation⁴ and the extent to which it successfully fulfils this objective needs to be assessed

significantly influences the creation of a legal system that is fair, inclusive, and accessible to all, irrespective of their socio-economic backgrounds. Legal aid as to be given by the Legal Aid Council of Nigeria is described to include the assistance of a legal practitioner including assistance usually given by a private legal practitioner both in preliminary steps incidental to a proceeding and legal representation in a proceeding itself.⁵

Legal Aid Council of Nigeria

The Legal Aid Act of 2011, formally creates the Legal Aid Council as a distinct legal entity, with the explicit mandate of providing crucial legal aid and ensuring equitable access to justice for individuals with limited means. The Council is thus by the above provision, endowed with the legal status to initiate legal proceedings as well as defend against them, while concurrently having the mandate to offer legal guidance and assistance.

Procedure for the Application for Legal Aid

The procedure for the application for the grant of Legal aid given by the legal aid council is provided for in the Legal Aid Council's Regulations of 2011. Legal Advice is to be given for free in any office of the council, in court, in police stations and in prisons for civil or criminal matters by legal practitioners appointed by the Legal Aid Council or in the service of the council.⁶ In regards to the eligibility for legal aid, The Legal Aid Council's Regulations of 2011 contains provisions to the effect that a person is eligible for legal aid IF and only IF such person has no income of any type or the income he has does not exceed the national minimum wage or where the court refers his case to Legal Aid Council in accordance to Form LAC 1 Criminal.⁷

Additionally, in situations where such person's income exceeds the minimum wage, legal aid may be granted if obtaining legal aid services outside the legal aid scheme will place the person in the same position as an applicant with no income or will place the person in the same position as an applicant whose income does not exceed the national minimum wage. In this circumstance however, such a person may be required to make a contribution towards the cost of legal services rendered to him and on his behalf.⁸

For Civil matters, there are additional requirements which include that The applicant's interest cannot be satisfied by any other process except litigation. (b) The Council had employed other dispute resolution mechanisms to no avail. (c) The nature and circumstances of the matter are such to be manifestly unsuitable to any other form of dispute resolution except litigation. (d) The cost value of the case would not exceed the input required by the Council. (e) The resultant end of the litigation would fundamentally alter the life of the applicant. (f) The applicant had not in any way perverted the cause of justice in the particular case.⁹ Now, persons applying for the grant of legal aid has to fill certain forms. For criminal cases Form LAC 2 and for civil cases, Form LAC 3.¹⁰

In furtherance of their mandate and to fulfil their functions, the legal aid council has launched two major initiatives. Namely the Police Duty Solicitors Scheme (PDSS) and the One Stop Claims Shop for Victims of Motor Accidents (OSCAR).¹¹

Access to Justice and the Legal Aid Council

Financial accessibility in the provision of legal aid is necessary in ensuring access to justice. This therefore implies that the criteria for accessing legal aid services should be such that the criteria for access legal aid should not be a criterion that is so narrow, limited and stringent as to exclude persons who actually need the assistance but fail to meet criteria because it is too restrictive. The eligibility criteria must also be sensitive to the current state of the economy and the financial circumstances of individuals within that economy. This adaptability is crucial to prevent the exclusion of those genuinely in need due to criteria that do not accurately reflect the economic realities faced by many seeking legal aid. Financial accessibility within the legal aid council's regulations is limited due to the narrow scope of the minimum wage set as the eligibility benchmark. The current minimum wage, which stands at 33,000 naira, doesn't accurately mirror the living standards in Nigeria.

Many individuals earning above this threshold still grapple with dire poverty. Additionally, the lengthy duration of cases and the associated high costs of litigation often surpass this minimum wage. This scenario implies that even individuals earning above the minimum wage might struggle to cover legal expenses, necessitating the need for legal aid. It is thus important to reassess the reliance on the 'minimum wage' as the criteria for determining eligibility for legal aid as the existing benchmark seems to not consider actual financial constraints individuals face when dealing with legal matters. Guidelines should therefore be devised and put in place to holistically evaluate an individual's need for legal aid, irrespective of whether their income surpasses the minimum wage. This would ensure a more inclusive approach, acknowledging that financial strain from legal proceedings isn't solely contingent on meeting or exceeding this wage threshold.

However, the regulations' acknowledgment of scenarios where legal aid can extend to individuals exceeding the minimum wage is commendable. Additionally, the provision allowing for contributions from applicants in situations where it's deemed necessary also reflects a balanced approach. This provision recognizes that while an individual might exceed the minimum wage, extraordinary circumstances or exceptionally high legal costs might still necessitate support through legal aid. Thus while the current reliance on the minimum wage as a determinant for legal aid eligibility falls short, the acknowledgment of exceptions and the allowance for applicant contributions in certain cases demonstrate a positive step towards inclusivity and fair access to legal assistance. Nevertheless, revising the criteria to consider broader financial constraints would ensure a more equitable and effective legal aid system and thus guarantee a greater access to justice.

Geographical accessibility is also important to ensure access to justice. In terms of geographical accessibility, the Legal aid council has at state offices in every in state of the country with their headquarters in the Federal Capital territory, Abuja. The council also as at present has 23 legal aid centres in 17 states.¹² The addresses of their offices are available on the legal aid council's website.¹³ While having centres in each state is commendable and fulfils part of the threshold for geographical accessibility, the threshold of true accessibility encompasses a broader scope. Geographical accessibility involves ensuring that individuals can access legal aid services

regardless of their location, encompassing the distribution of legal aid offices, service availability in rural areas, and outreach programs targeting marginalized communities. While having centres in each state is commendable, the current setup does not fully meet the criteria for accessibility, especially concerning service availability in rural areas. A critical fact to note is that these state offices are primarily located in the capital cities of the respective states, limiting accessibility for individuals in rural or remote regions. Moreover, the presence of legal aid centres in only 17 out of the 36 states in Nigeria represents less than half of the states, further restricting access for a significant portion of the population.

In terms of outreach programs aimed at reaching marginalized communities, the Police Duty Solicitor scheme initiated by the Legal Aid Council operates in only 8 out of the country's 36 states.¹⁴ This limited coverage indicates a gap in extending legal aid services to those in dire need, residing in areas which are currently not covered by this scheme. Thus, while acknowledging the presence of state offices and legal aid centres across several states, the current setup falls short of achieving full geographical accessibility. The uneven distribution of centres, concentration in capital cities, and the limited reach of outreach programs impede comprehensive access to legal aid and, consequently, access to justice for a significant portion of Nigeria's population.

Analysis of Available Yearly Reports of the Legal Aid Council of Nigeria

Year	Total Applications	Criminal Cases	Civil Cases	Applications Granted	Applications Rejected	Completed Cases	Pending Cases
2006	5503	4427	1076	5309	194	3077	2232
2007	5099	4024	1075	4006	93	3558	1448
2008	4698	3738	960	4675	23	3191	1484
2009	5099	3781	1318	5099	0	3129	1970
2010	5379	4257	1122	5375	4	3498	1877
2011	7608	6054	1554	7608	0	4260	3348
2012	11336	9206	2130	11336	0	6323	5013
2013	13579	9979	3800	13579	0	8351	5228
2014	15350	10452	4898	15350	0	10228	5122
2015	8224	4988	3236	8224	0	5360	2864

These figures imply that the legal aid council provides legal to people within the range 4000-16,000. This commendable but taking into cognizance the population of Nigeria there is room for improvement.

Activities and Interventions of Legal Aids Council in Nigeria

From 2016 till date, the Legal Aid Council has not provided yearly statistics. However, notable activities and interventions have been reported in various instances, showcasing some of the council's activities and achievements. In an article posted on the legal aid website on December 2020, it was reported that the Council defended some defendants at court sittings, resulting in the discharge of nine inmates facing various charges and the grant of bail to 23 inmates under liberal terms.

An article from January 8, 2021, mentioned the discharge of three accused individuals on charges of conspiracy and armed robbery, cases that originally date back to 2017.¹⁵

On October 15, 2022, an article highlighted the provision of legal aid to Adamu Abdullahi and 100 others in custody at Kirikiri Maximum and Minimum Centres. These individuals had been remanded in various correctional facilities since 2009¹⁶.

These articles shed light on the Council's efforts in providing legal aid services, despite the absence of annual statistical reports during these years.

The Office of the Public Defender Lagos State

The Office of the Public Defender was established on July 24th, 2000, during the tenure of His Excellency Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu, the then Governor of the State. Its core objective, to provide free legal services to the indigent population of Lagos State, addressing a critical need within Nigeria's Justice System administration. This initiative aims to offer support to those who could not afford legal representation ultimately ensuring equitable access to justice for all.¹⁷

As stated by Banji Fayomi, it was reported that within the years 2000 and 2007, according to the Office, the Mediation Centre has received 5,600 petitions at an average of 30 petitions per day. It has also succeeded among other things in releasing from prison 250 juveniles. It has also helped to collect over N6 million for people who took their cases to them. These settlements involved rents, unpaid salaries, payment for work done etc. Part of the recovery was the payment of N950, 000.00 by a textile company which had been owing its workers. Widows have also been assisted in collecting death benefits. The efforts of the Office in the January 27th 2002 Ikeja Military Cantonment bomb blast is also worth mentioning. The OPD collated the names of the dead, injured and missing persons and processed claims on behalf of the victims and their relatives. The efforts of the Office paid off as the Federal Government paid the sum of N500, 000 to relatives of each of the dead victims. In an article posted in the Vanguard newspaper on Feb 29 2012, it was reported that in its then 12 years of existence, OPD, has handled 34,100 cases.

In 2019, it was reported that the Office received over Four Thousand (4,000), walk in petitions, offered free legal representation to 13,787 person in civil and criminal matters at various High and Magistrate Courts in Lagos State There were also 73 rescue missions carried out by Officers of the Office to rescue children in distress. The sum of Thirty-two million Naira (N32, 000,000) was recovered on behalf of clients represented in Courts. In 2020, the Office has received over One Thousand (1,000) walk in petitions so far, carried out 34 rescue missions, and recovered over Eight million naira (8,000,000) for clients.

Private Institutions and Non-Governmental Organisations

In addition to governmental institutions, Legal aid is also provided by other private institutions and NGO'S such as Legal Advocacy Response to Drug Initiatives (LARDI), International Federation of Women Lawyers (FIDA).

Legal Advocacy Response for Drug Initiatives (LARDI)

LARDI is a non-profit organization dedicated to providing pro bono legal representation to financially disadvantaged individuals facing drug-related charges. This organization is exclusively focused on giving legal aid for strictly drug related offences.¹⁸ The emphasis on drug-related offenses is particularly crucial due to the exclusion of individuals arrested in this category from receiving legal aid services under the Legal Aid Act of 2011. The organization also focuses on advocacy, partnering with stakeholders with the goal of reforming the legal and institutional framework to ensure the appropriate treatment for drug arrestees. The organization canvasses for the right of drug users to proper treatment and rehabilitation while discouraging drug abuse.

LARDI throughout the Years

The organization, founded in 2018, regularly publishes quarterly reports in the form of newsletters. However, it's worth noting that some reports for certain quarters are unavailable. Here's a summary of the available reports from the Legal Advocacy Response for Drug Initiatives:

In 2020, pro-bono lawyers associated with the Legal Advocacy Response to Drugs Initiative (LARDI) had assisted 62 indigent drug offenders, successfully resolving their tough legal issues and securing their release from correctional facilities across the country. Additionally, these lawyers were handling 76 more drug-related cases pending in various Nigerian courts, totalling 138 cases. April 2021's report highlighted that during the first quarter of that year, LARDI members defended 22 indigent drug arrestees, concluding 13 cases. In the third quarter of 2021, the organization handled a total of 40 cases. Moving to March 2023, LARDI reported handling 28 cases in the first quarter: 19 cases concluded and 9 pending. Their newsletter for the third quarter of 2023 mentioned that the organization dealt with 7 cases, concluding 4 cases and leaving 3 pending.

In addition to LARDI, other private institutions provide legal aid including the International Federation of Women Lawyers (FIDA), dedicated to championing the rights of women and children. FIDA focuses on eliminating discrimination, violence, and abuse from society by leveraging legal frameworks. Alongside other endeavours, they offer legal support to women and children. Another organization, the Legal Defence and Assistance Project (LEDAP), is a human rights advocate providing legal aid and working on issues like prison overcrowding and death penalty cases. These organizations, among others, are part of the legal aid scheme, filling gaps left by the Legal Aid Council and catering to specific groups, contributing to the diverse landscape of legal assistance and helping to achieve the overall goal of ensuring that access to justice is available to all.

Legal Aid in other Jurisdictions

Germany

Germany's judicare system is unique in its reliance on a combination of private and public resources. Individuals needing legal aid approach private lawyers directly, who then receive

compensation from the state for taking their case. This ensures a wider pool of experienced lawyers available for those seeking aid, compared to systems relying solely on public defenders.¹⁹ Essentially, lawyers first assess the case's merit, evaluating if it has a reasonable chance of success. This merit assessment helps prevent frivolous lawsuits and ensures that aid goes to individuals with cases genuinely needing legal representation. Following the merit assessment, the lawyer further evaluates the individual's financial situation to determine their eligibility for financial assistance. This ensures that legal aid reaches those who genuinely cannot afford legal representation on their own. Ultimately, court has the final say in approving legal aid applications and determines if a person is to be granted legal aid or not²⁰.

Legal aid in Germany comes in the form of been granted exemptions from court costs and the payment of counsel fees which is paid by the state. There are regulations in place regarding the amount allocated in legal aid cases paid to the lawyer. The structure and organization of legal aid in Germany can also be said to be deeply intertwined with social law, wherein the concept of assistance in legal proceedings is rooted in principles of social assistance.²¹ This means that procedural assistance, as governed by the Civil Procedure Code (CPC), is considered a specialized aspect of social law. Costs associated with litigation include a state fee, typically dictated by laws on judicial expenses.

England

The Legal Aid, Sentencing and Punishment of Offenders Act 2012 (LASPO) outlines the framework for civil and criminal legal aid provision.²² Financial eligibility criteria are detailed in section 21 of LASPO and related regulations, while section 23 covers contributions toward legal aid costs. LASPO specifies areas eligible for legal aid, such as community care, mental health, housing, and family law related to child protection or abuse.²³ In the UK, eligibility for Legal Aid hinges on three key assessments: Means Testing, Merits Testing, and Interests of Justice.

To qualify for civil legal aid, applicants must pass both income and capital tests. The gross income test sets a maximum limit, currently at £2,657 per month, above which applicants are ineligible for civil legal aid unless they receive qualifying benefits. If applicants pass the gross income test, their disposable income and capital are considered.²⁴ Eligibility requires monthly disposable income below £733 and disposable capital below £8,000. However, even if applicants meet these criteria, they may still be required to contribute to legal aid costs. Contributions are applicable if monthly disposable income exceeds £315 or disposable capital exceeds £3,000, depending on the type of legal aid sought.²⁵

Key Differences between the Legal Aid Schemes in Nigeria, England, and Germany.

A key difference between the German and Nigerian legal aid system lies in the body responsible for granting legal aid. In Germany, the courts themselves decide whether to grant legal aid, while Nigeria has a separate body for this purpose. This divergence presents both advantages and challenges within the Nigerian context. The simplicity and efficiency of Germany's court-based system have notable advantages. By entrusting legal aid decisions to the judiciary, there's a streamlined process that eliminates additional bureaucratic layers. This direct approach offers

clarity and expediency for those seeking assistance, as they can directly petition the courts for aid.

Additionally, judges directly involved in the case can assess the merits of the legal aid request alongside the legal issues at hand. This allows them to determine if the case truly warrants state-funded representation. However, it is important to recognize that this system functions well within the context of Germany's inquisitorial legal system. Inquisitorial systems place a more active role on the judge or investigator in uncovering the facts of a case. This allows the judge overseeing the legal aid application to have a better understanding of the case's complexity and the need for legal representation.²⁶

On the flipside, Nigeria's legal system, operating under an adversarial model, where parties advocate for their interests before an impartial adjudicator, requires a nuanced understanding of each party's position, which a specialized body might be better equipped to assess. Despite these differences, there is potential value in adopting elements of the German system in Nigeria. A hybrid approach, granting both the courts and a designated body the authority to decide on legal aid applications, could offer a balance between efficiency and fairness. This model would leverage the expertise of both judicial and administrative entities, ensuring thorough consideration of applicants' needs while maintaining a degree of procedural expediency.

The Legal aid system in England is very similar to that of Nigeria as there is a separate body responsible for the provision for legal aid in both countries. However, a difference lies in the criteria of means testing. While the 'minimum wage' is the criteria for accessing legal aid services from the Legal Aid Council in Nigeria, in England, eligibility hinges on income of below £12,475.²⁷

Challenges of legal aid in Nigeria

The legal aid scheme in Nigeria is a critical component of the justice system, aiming to ensure that all citizens, regardless of their financial circumstances, have access to legal representation and assistance. However, the effectiveness of this scheme is hampered by various challenges. These challenges include;

1. Financial Challenges
2. Lack of awareness
3. Geographical limitations
4. Systemic issues within the legal system

Financial Challenges

Financial constraint is a significant challenge to the effectiveness of the legal aid scheme in Nigeria with one of the primary issues being insufficient funding. Despite the critical role that legal aid plays in ensuring access to justice for marginalized and underprivileged populations, the allocation of funds for legal aid programs is often inadequate and this challenge has remained persistent. In 2016, the past chairman of the Governing board of the Legal Aid Council, Chief Bolaji Ayorinde, SAN stated that the council was grappling with challenges of

poor funding and logistics. This inadequacy results in limited resources thus, legal aid providers are unable to offer comprehensive services to those in need. It also hampers efforts to expand the reach of legal aid to remote areas and communities. Government funding for legal aid also often fluctuates or fails to meet the growing demand for legal aid services and without reliable and predictable funding streams, legal aid providers struggle to maintain consistent operations and plan for long-term initiatives.

Geographical Limitations

Access to legal aid services in Nigeria is also hindered by limitations in coverage. Geographic limitations in particular, present a significant hurdle to accessing legal aid services in Nigeria as legal aid centres and providers are often concentrated in urban areas or more populous regions and these providers struggle to extend their reach to rural and remote areas. As a result, individuals living in these remote areas face difficulties in accessing legal representation and assistance. It must be said that factors such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of electricity, limited transportation options, and geographical isolation further exacerbate these challenges, making it challenging for legal aid providers to establish and maintain a presence in these regions. Thus, the state of Nigeria as a developing country also affects the provision of legal aid. In 2019, a study by the World Justice Project on access to justice revealed that in Nigeria, out of the 60% who experienced a legal problem in the preceding two years, only 25% were able to access assistance, with only 13% being able to access legal aid. Thus, the uneven distribution of legal aid resources across different regions perpetuates disparities in access to justice. This geographic imbalance not only limits the availability of legal aid but also ties into another challenge facing the legal aid scheme in Nigeria which is lack of awareness.

Lack of Awareness

Lack of awareness presents a significant challenge to the effectiveness of the legal aid scheme in Nigeria. Many Nigerians, particularly those living in remote areas are simply unaware. They might endure unfair treatment, land grabs, or exploitative contracts without realizing they have legal recourse. Without this basic understanding, they would not even know that they qualify for legal aid in the first place. Even if legal aid services exist, people who are unaware of them can't utilize them. This creates a situation where the intended beneficiaries, the most vulnerable in the society remain without proper legal support. A study conducted by HiiL in 2018 corroborates this noting that the legal aid scheme, whose main purpose is to serve as a safety net for individuals with no means to procure the services of a lawyer, was not visible enough and that only two out of ten Nigerians engage formal institutions to solve their problems with the police being used but courts and lawyers rarely used. The institutional capacity of the legal aid scheme in Nigeria is also hindered by inadequacies in the number of legal aid providers and a lack of training and resources for legal aid lawyers. These challenges impact the quality and effectiveness of legal aid services, limiting their ability to meet the diverse needs of the population. Legal aid organizations, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and pro bono legal clinics, are often understaffed. The shortage of legal aid providers is particularly acute in remote areas, where the need for legal assistance may be high but resources are scarce. As a result, many individuals in these areas are unable to access

legal aid services, forcing them to navigate the legal system without adequate support and representation.

Systemic issues within the legal system

The systemic issues of corruption and bureaucratic inefficiencies within the judicial system also impact the effectiveness institutions providing legal aid in Nigeria. When cases are in court for extended periods due to delays, inefficiencies, or corruption, it directly affects the effectiveness of these institutions. In essence, the intertwined nature of the legal aid institutions with the court systems means that any issue plaguing the judiciary indirectly affects the effectiveness of these institutions.

CONCLUSION

In evaluating the effectiveness of the institutional framework for the regulation of legal aid in Nigeria, it is evident that strides have been made to provide legal aid for individuals in the country. These strides include the promulgation of laws governing legal aid, establishing a body to govern the provision of legal aid and the efforts of both governmental and non-governmental institutions. However, despite the strides made, the effectiveness of the legal aid institutions in Nigeria is hindered by various challenges ranging from limited funding and lack of awareness to systemic inefficiencies and geographical inaccessibility. As such there is a need to effectively address these challenges to further strengthen the effectiveness of legal aid institutions in Nigeria. Addressing these challenges will thus require implementing targeted reforms and the collaboration of institutions like the judiciary, the police force and policy makers who are linked to the legal aid system.

Recommendations

Use of Public Defenders

The Legal Aid Council of Nigeria possesses the authority to enlist lawyers serving in the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) scheme to provide assistance to individuals needing legal aid. For this recommendation to be effective, it is imperative for the Legal Aid Council to offer each participating lawyer in the NYSC scheme a monthly living and accommodation allowances commensurate with the prevailing standards of living. This financial support would not only incentivize participation but also ensure that NYSC members can fully dedicate themselves to their roles as public defenders. Additionally, as there is nationwide deployment of NYSC members, they possess a unique advantage in reaching remote communities where legal aid services are often scarce. Their presence in these areas can help raise awareness about the Legal Aid Council and its services, thereby extending the council's outreach and impact.

Use of university-based Legal Aid Clinics

Another impactful approach to bolstering legal aid services in Nigeria involves encouraging universities offering law degrees to establish legal aid clinics. These clinics, supervised by experienced law professors, can serve as valuable legal advice centres for underserved communities. By providing law students with opportunities to participate in pro bono legal

work under faculty guidance, these clinics can cultivate a strong pro bono spirit among future lawyers. University based legal aid clinics can also address the challenge of lack of awareness as they can serve as community outreach and referral centres, raising awareness about the existence of legal aid services offered by the Legal Aid Council and other legal service providers.

Adequate funding

Legal aid institutions should be adequately funded by government to enhance its activities.

Eligibility criteria

It is recommended that the eligibility criteria for legal aid under the Legal Aid Act 2011 be revised and amended to align with the current socio-economic realities and standards of living prevalent in Nigerian society. To adapt to the dynamic nature of societal conditions, it is essential that the eligibility criteria for legal aid services remain flexible and subject to periodic review. Granting the Chairman of the Legal Aid Council the authority to adjust these criteria as necessary will enable a more effective approach.

Waiving of filing fees

Financial constraint is a persistent challenge facing the legal aid scheme in Nigeria and in addition to the above, a potential solution lies in legislation that waives court costs, such as filing fees, for cases undertaken by the LAC and other verified legal aid providers. This approach, similar to the existing system in the Lagos State Public Defender's Office, would reduce the financial burden on those seeking legal aid. Legal aid providers should also explore other funding avenues beyond government allocation such as humanitarian grants and contributions from private donors.

Implementing court mandated legal aid for individuals.

Drawing inspiration from Germany's legal aid system, it is recommended that Nigerian courts be empowered to approve applications for legal aid or mandate the provision of legal representation in certain circumstances.

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- 25) Ministry of Justice, ‘The Current Legal Aid Financial Eligibility Rules – Summary’ <https://consult.justice.gov.uk/digital-communications/legal-aid-eligibility-and-universal-credit/supporting_documents/annexcsummaryofcurrentlegalaidfinancialegibilityrules.pdf> accessed 11th March 2024.
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